

Deutsche Initiative für
Netzwerkinformation e.V.

DINI CERTIFICATE FOR OPEN ACCESS PUBLICATION SERVICES 2022

This preprint is published under the [Attribution 4.0 International \(CC BY 4.0\)](#) license.
The document is available online under <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8324738>. It is the
authorized translation of:

DINI-Zertifikat für Open-Access-Publikationsdienste 2022 (2022). Ed. DINI-Arbeitsgruppe
Elektronisches Publizieren. Online: <https://doi.org/10.18452/24678>.

Content

About DINI.....	3
1 Aims and Content of the DINI Certificate	3
1.1 Background	3
1.2 Aims and Objectives of the DINI Certificate	4
1.3 Content of the Certificate.....	5
1.4 DINI-ready: Modularizing the Certification Process.....	6
2 Criteria.....	7
2.1 Visibility of the Service.....	7
2.2 Guidelines (Policy).....	9
2.3 Support of Authors and Publishers.....	10
2.4 Legal Aspects	12
2.5 Information Security.....	17
2.6 Indexing and Interfaces	18
2.7 Open Metrics	20
2.8 Long-term Archiving	21
2.9 OAI interface.....	22
2.10 OAI-PMH: Additional Requirements	25
2.10.1 Open Access Document Set.....	25
2.10.2 Sets for disciplinary grouping.....	26
2.10.3 Document and Publication Type Set.....	30
2.10.4 Publication Status Set.....	33
2.10.5 Deleted Documents	34
2.10.6 Data Flow Control	35

2.11 Metadata Requirements of the OAI Interface	36
3 Awarding and Evaluation	40
4 Glossary	41
Open Access Publication Services / Service / Publication Service.....	41
Institutional Open Access Repository	42
Cross-institutional Repository	42
Disciplinary Open Access Repository	42
Open Access Journal.....	42
Digital Collection	42
Research-data Repository	43
Current Research Information System (CRIS).....	43
University Bibliography	43
Hosting Service.....	43
Aggregator	43
Author/Publisher	44
Operator, Technical Operator	44
Data Provider	44
Deposit License	44
Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC).....	44
Document.....	44
Document Server	45
Primary Publication	45
Landing Page.....	45
Metadata	45
User	45
Usage Rights / Copyright.....	46
Open Access.....	46
Open Access Policy	46
Persistent Identifier (PI)	46
Rights Holder	46
Subject Headings of the German National Bibliography.....	47
Service Provider.....	47
Creator	47
Secondary Publication	47
Authors.....	47
Additional authors of earlier versions:	50
Membership application form for DINI e. V.	51
Legal notice.....	51

About DINI

The development of modern information and communication technologies causes a change in the information infrastructures of higher education institutions and other research institutions. This change is a major topic within higher education in Germany, and more than ever requires agreements, cooperation, recommendations, and standards. The Deutsche Initiative für Netzwerkinformation (DINI, German Initiative for Network Information) supports this development.

DINI was founded to advance the improvement of the information and communication services and the necessary development of the information infrastructures at the universities as well as on regional and national levels. Agreements and the distribution of tasks among the infrastructure institutions and facilities can significantly extend the range of information technology and services. This requires the joint development of standards and recommendations.

DINI is an initiative of three organizations:

- AMH (*Arbeitsgemeinschaft der Medienzentren der deutschen Hochschulen*; Consortium of German University Media Centers),
- dbv (*Deutscher Bibliotheksverband Sektion 4: Wissenschaftliche Universalbibliotheken*; German Library Association, Section 4: Academic Universal Libraries),
- ZKI (*Zentren für Kommunikation und Informationsverarbeitung in Lehre und Forschung e. V.*; Association of German University Computing Centers)

with scientific institutions and organizations.

DINI has the following goals:

- Publicize and recommend best practices;
- Encourage and support the formulation, application and further development of standards as well as distribute recommendations regarding their application;
- Register and advertise Competence Centers using modern web-based technologies;
- Improve interdisciplinary exchange through congresses, workshops, expert conferences, etc.;
- Advertise new funding programs and encourage new programs.

1 Aims and Content of the DINI Certificate

1.1 Background

Publishing is an important pillar for the advancement of scientific knowledge and of science as a whole. It is not established in the field of research. Characteristics of scientific publishing include

- a. the organization of effective communication between researchers (between → *authors* and all potential recipients, i.e. securing an adequate dissemination),

- b. a high degree of trustworthiness (e.g. with regard to copyrights, priority, authenticity, and quality of content) that is communicated to the → *users* of publications (i.e. researchers), and
- c. sustainability and verifiability (persistent citations, long-term availability, traceability of the steps on the way to publication).

The present catalog of criteria translates these general expectations of scientific publishing into concrete minimum requirements of → *Open Access publication services*. As platforms for the publication and presentation of scientific and scholarly works these represent important hubs in the scientific communication process. As Open Access services they facilitate the dissemination and democratization of knowledge.

The term → *Open Access publication services* comprises the following services (see also Definitions in section 4):

- Institutional Open Access repositories
- Cross-institutional repositories
- Disciplinary Open Access repositories
- Open Access journals

The DINI Certificate was created by the *DINI-Arbeitsgemeinschaft Elektronisches Publizieren* (DINI Electronic Publishing Consortium - <https://dini.de/e-pub1>) and first introduced in 2004. Experts representing the consortium update the Certificate's catalog of criteria every three years to account for current requirements and development, and it is subsequently translated into several other languages. The present certificate is the seventh version that includes an initial step towards internationalization. By way of example, the catalog of criteria has been adapted to meet Austrian requirements so that publication services from Austria can also be certified.

1.2 Aims and Objectives of the DINI Certificate

The DINI Certificate for Open Access publication services essentially serves two main goals:

1. **Improve the publication infrastructure** for electronic publishing;
2. **Strengthen** → *Open Access-based forms of publishing*
3. **Integrability** of Open Access publication services in line with principles of open and transparent science and research
4. **Seamless linking** of Open Access publication services to process chains for research (data) infrastructures

The DINI Certificate with its underlying catalog of criteria facilitates reaching these goals in the following manner:

1. The DINI Certificate communicates **benchmarks, guidelines, and best practices**; it contributes to a general understanding of the principles of electronic scientific publishing. Through its detailed catalog of requirements and the permanent practical evaluation, the DINI Certificate offers a basis for further discussions and the regular adaptation and editing of requirements.
2. The DINI Certificate **yields effects for** → **operators**. Minimum requirements and recommendations form a catalog of aspects (and consequently a series of steps) that

must be considered when creating an → *Open Access publication service* for electronic publishing. As such, it serves to qualify personnel responsible for the implementation and operation of a publication service.

3. The DINI Certificate **yields effects for funding bodies** (supporters of information infrastructure, operating institutions). It shows the effort, expense and degree of professionalism it requires to operate Open Access publication services, while also demonstrating the additional benefits of a solid, standardized and sustainable service. The DINI Certificate also provides researchers with valuable guidance. By way of example, it can help them to determine the organizational and technical basis on which Open Access publications are to be published and on which publication services are to be set up.
4. The DINI Certificate **yields effects for researchers** who use Open Access publication services as → *authors* and/or *publishers*. In this sense, the DINI Certificate is an easy to recognize quality seal for consumers. It designates publication services as trustworthy partners within their institution or discipline.
5. The DINI Certificate aims to bring about an **improvement to a publication service's quality** in terms of– among others–organizational and technical sustainability, interoperability and transparency. This effect is best seen in services that are already certified. But it can also be observed in the use of the certificate as a guideline for the creation and further development of new services, even if no official certification process follows.
6. The DINI Certificate's seal works as a **mark of quality** and encourages use of the services.

1.3 Content of the Certificate

The DINI Certificate's catalog of criteria and its associated certification process are aimed at → *Open Access publishing services* and their inherent core components and processes.

In this document, operators and providers of Open Access publication services are primarily considered to be scientific institutions (universities, universities of applied sciences, research institutions, etc.) and organizations (professional associations), but also non-commercial and commercial publishing entities that publish Open Access. Open Access publication services in this sense must be addressed and described with a view to the kinds of publications they are intended for (institutional, disciplinary, and formal aspects). They are characterized by the following core processes:

- Services for → *authors and publishers/editors*;
- Intake, treatment and long-term storage of the → *documents* and → *metadata* of a publication;
- Public availability of the publications, ensuring findability for human and machine-based access necessary for comprehensive add-on services, as well as the transfer of metadata and, where applicable, the transfer of publications.

The following core components realize or support the abovementioned core processes.

- An underlying **organizational structure** (not part of the certificate)
- The **technical basic system**;
- **User interfaces** (esp. web frontend, → deposit license);
- **Technical interfaces** (esp. OAI interface).

2 Criteria

The DINI Certificate comprises eleven criteria that are described in detail in this section. The criteria are:

- [Criterion 1 – Visibility of the Service](#)
- [Criterion 2 – Guidelines \(Policy\)](#)
- [Criterion 3 – Support of Authors and Publishers](#)
- [Criterion 4 – Legal Aspects](#)
- [Criterion 5 – Information Security](#)
- [Criterion 6 – Indexing and Interfaces](#)
- [Criterion 7 – Open Metrics](#)
- [Criterion 8 – Long-term Archiving](#)
- [Criterion 9 – OAI Interface](#)
- [Criterion 10 – OAI-PMH: Additional Requirements](#)
- [Criterion 11 – Metadata Requirements of the OAI Interface](#)

The eleven criteria are split into minimum requirements (M) and recommendations (R), which must be met to qualify for DINI certification. Additional recommendations are provided to offer guidance in the sense of best-practice solutions and provide future tendencies in the development of Open Access publication services. These recommendations do not have to be met to qualify for certification with the current DINI Certificate. However, as DINI plans to continuously update the certificate it is likely that in later versions of the DINI Certificate, some of these recommendations will be minimum requirements.

Each criterion is introduced by a short paragraph that explains the criterion and the reason(s) for its being a requirement. The requirements in the respective criteria are formulated like a check list to allow answering simply with yes or no. Each point is accompanied by explanations of termini, interpretations or definitions, rationales or examples.

2.1 Visibility of the Service

Greater visibility and a potentially higher recognition are characteristic advantages of electronic publications, especially when published → *Open Access*. To make the most of this potential, the entire range of an underlying service's offers must be widely advertised. It has to be visible not only to the immediate and individual user—regardless of whether one wants to read a specific publication or use it in another way, or if one wants to publish a document—but also to comprehensive or discipline specific services. These can be search engines or other referencing services, as well as other automated processes. Besides the necessary technical interfaces described in [Criterion 6 – Indexing and Interfaces](#), the registration of a local service with the pertinent agencies or listing services is crucial. These agencies serve as facilitators between different distributed Open Access publication services and comprehensive or discipline specific services.

Minimum Requirements

M.1-1 The entire range of services must be available online on the web.

⇒ This refers to a service's homepage from which both publication workflow and access to already published documents are possible.

M.1-2 The service's homepage must be referenced in a central location on the institution's homepage.

- ⇒ one or two clicks suffice to reach the service from the operating institution's homepage
 - ⇒ potential users must be guided as intuitively as possible from an institution's, a research facility's or a library's central website to the service
-

M.1-3 The service is registered and listed in the list of BASE sources on the DINI website as well as in the Bielefeld Academic Search Engine (BASE) with a permanently available base URL.

⇒ The base URL is the internet address where the service's OAI interface can be reached (see also [M.6-6](#) in [section 2.6 – Indexing and Interfaces](#), as well as [section 2.9 - OAI Interface Criteria](#)).

⇒ DINI list (see <https://dini.de/dienste-projekte/publikationsdienste>)

⇒ BASE (see <https://www.base-search.net/about/en/suggest.php?>)

M.1-4 Open Access publications are clearly marked on the website.

⇒ Limiting a search to Open Access publications (e.g. through checkboxes and faceting) is possible. Additionally, Open Access publications are clearly designated in browsing or result lists, e.g. with a logo.

⇒ The goal is to increase visibility of Open Access publications in publication services such as research information systems and publication databases.

⇒ Should a publication service offer Open Access publications only, this basic characteristic should be made clear on the website. In this case, the designation of the individual publication as Open Access is not required.

Recommendations

R.1-1 The service and, where applicable, its OAI interface are listed with current data in at least one additional registry.

- ⇒ Among these are the list of registered OAI data providers (see <https://www.openarchives.org/Register/BrowseSites>), OpenAIRE (see <https://provide.openaire.eu>), OpenDOAR (see <https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/opensoar>), DOAJ (see <https://www.doaj.org>).
-

R.1-2 All documents published with the service are available via links.

- ⇒ This facilitates finding a document by way of search engines (robots or spiders). Documents that can only be found through a search request and that are not available via a hyperlink will not be found by search engines.
-

R.1-3 Links to or privacy-compliant integration (two-click solution) of social media are offered on the landing page of each individual publication.

- ⇒ Links from social-media services to documents increase their visibility.
-

R.1-4 The service supports search engine optimization (SEO).

- ⇒ To increase search engine visibility, the service supports the search engines' and initiatives' means to improve the documents' findability, e.g. support of vocabularies (e.g. <https://schema.org>), qualified links (e.g. <https://signposting.org>) or guidelines (e.g. Google

Scholar Inclusion Guidelines for Webmasters,
<https://scholar.google.com/scholar/inclusion.html>).

2.2 Guidelines (Policy)

Reliability and transparency play a major role when providing Open Access publication services. It is crucial for the respective operators to describe the offered services clearly and make statements on content-related criteria and on the technical operations (e.g. on document types, intended users, sustainability of the service) in publicly available guidelines. Such guidelines, also referred to here as a policy, represent the operator's self-commitment towards both potential and actual users of the services.

Minimum Requirements

M.2-1 The operators publicly provide a policy that describes the services.

⇒ The operators in the DINI Certificate's understanding are the providers of the service who hold responsibility for the entire service. For repositories this is the responsible institution, for other services (e.g. an Open Access journal) this is typically the publisher(s) or editor(s).

⇒ The policy—as a self-commitment—is a stand-alone document. A list of FAQ is not sufficient.

⇒ The policy must be linked to directly from the service's main page and must be a document in and of itself.

The policy comprises statements on the following:

M.2-2 A definition of the operators' rights and obligations.

⇒ This includes a description of the service and statements on for whom and under what conditions it is provided.

M.2-3 A definition of the authors' rights and obligations when using the service to publish their documents. This also applies to publishers who are not operators in the sense of M.2-1.

⇒ This includes, e.g. a statement on what copyrights the copyright holders transfer to the operators.

⇒ See also the explanations in [section 2.4 – Legal Aspects](#).

M.2-4 A description of the document types published via the service, and requirements with regard to the documents' content and technical quality.

⇒ This corresponds to a collection mandate. Additional quality criteria referring to content quality (e.g. peer review, author guidelines) and technical aspects (e.g. file formats) serve primarily as guidance for potential users.

M.2-5 A specification of the minimum timespan that documents published with the service will be available, plus the respective guarantee.

⇒ The specified timespans do not have to be identical for all documents but can depend on document or publication type, or on a document's technical or content quality. However, the chosen value must not fall below five years (see also [section 2.8 – Long-term Archiving](#)).

M.2-6 A statement on long-term archiving of the documents.

⇒ This includes a description of how the long-term archiving of the publications is either planned or ensured, e.g. by way of cooperation with another institution (see also [section 2.8 – Long-term Archiving](#), R.8-1).

M.2-7 A statement on the technical operation of the service.

⇒ This includes information on who is operating the service technically, and the service's basic performance parameters (especially availability).

M.2-8 A statement on Open Access.

⇒ This statement must clarify the position of the operators with regard to Open Access as well as point out those parts of the publications that might not be freely available in the sense of Open Access (including information about possible embargoes, request features, etc.).
⇒ The majority of the publications provided must be available in the sense of Open Access.
⇒ Should the institution operating the service (e.g. a university) have published an Open Access declaration, the policy is required to refer to it.

M.2-9 Information on how the service deals with document versions and deletions.

⇒ It must be noted specifically that documents cannot be altered after their publication and that a deletion is the exception (see [section 2.5 – Information Security](#), M.5-6, M.5-9, R.5-2).

Recommendations

R.2-1 Guidelines and recommendations for authors with regard to Open Access.

⇒ This is especially useful in a policy if the operating institution recommends or intends a certain practice, e.g. the self-archiving of publications (the “green road”), as published in an institutional Open Access declaration. Guidelines may vary according to document or publication type.

R.2-2 Naming and description of the tools used to provide the service.

⇒ This can include, e.g. the repository software, upload interfaces, versioning and authentication procedures as well as automated license definitions (for primary publications).

R.2-3 Information on the conditions under which third parties may use the repository's metadata.

⇒ See [Criterion 4 – Legal Aspects](#), R.4-5.

2.3 Support of Authors and Publishers

The aim is to support the entire publication process within the offered service. Those making use of the service to publish (→ *authors* and, where applicable, *publishers*) set great store on visible and well-structured information that answers key questions relating to electronic publishing. The relevant pages should at least be accessible via the service's website and may additionally be provided in other formats (e.g. flyers, brochures). The information may include external resources.

Minimum Requirements

M.3-1 A contact and advisory service is accessible via the website.

⇒ Contact options may include email addresses, phone numbers, etc. or contact forms on the web pages. It is not necessary to provide all of the above options, but at least one is mandatory.

⇒ Primary-publication services, e.g. Open Access journals, using an institution's infrastructure must differentiate between contact with the editorial team and contact for other areas of support.

M.3-2 Authors have the option to upload their documents intended for publication directly to the repository (e.g. via a web form) or to use other ways to add documents to the repository.

⇒ For Open Access journals this includes the option to submit articles for publication.

Information is provided in a central location to explain the steps involved in the process.

⇒ This requirement is superfluous if the operating institution (or publisher in the case of journals) organizes the entire document upload process.

M.3-3 Information on the relevant technical questions on electronic publishing is provided or linked to.

⇒ This includes information about Open Access and legal frameworks as well as tutorials on technical implementation, e.g. on the use of applicable file formats and how to upload electronic documents to the service.

⇒ Information on quality assurance is provided. This explicitly includes information on the respectively applicable code of scientific practice.

Reference for Germany: German Research Foundation (*Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft* – DFG) (see <https://wissenschaftliche-integritaet.de/en/>);

Reference for Austria: Austrian Agency for Research Integrity (*Österreichische Agentur für wissenschaftliche Integrität* – ÖAWI) (see <https://oeawi.at/en/>).

⇒ Open Access journals additionally provide publication guidelines for authors.

M.3.4 Relevant information resources with regard to copyright questions are referenced:

⇒ For secondary publication, resources include, e.g. a link to the Sherpa Romeo list (see <https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/romeo/>).

⇒ For the sake of information and transparency, advice is provided on key aspects such as licensing, liability, and use of the publication. Before the upload or the submission of a publication, authors are informed at a central location about the transfer of copyright to the operators associated with the upload. This information on the → *deposit license* or on standardized free licenses (e.g. Creative Commons) is available for download.

Recommendations

R.3-1 At least one of the following APIs is integrated to support clarification of rights:

The Sherpa Romeo API for authors (see <https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/api/>):

⇒ In the event of secondary publication, this allows authors to research during the upload process the general position of their publisher on the usage rights and copyrights they retain in accordance with their publishing contract.

- ⇒ Germany: Open Access API of the Electronic Journals Library (*Elektronische Zeitschriftenbibliothek* – EZB, see <https://ezb.uni-regensburg.de/services/oa-ezb.phtml>) for operators of the service:
- ⇒ The EZB Open Access API provides the Open Access rights for the publication of full texts pursuant to *Allianz-, National- or Konsortiallizenzen* in Germany.
- ⇒ Austria: Austrian Academic Library Consortium (*Kooperation E-Medien Österreich* – KEMÖ, see <https://www.kemoe.at/english/about-us>). KEMÖ provides Open Access rights to public full texts under consortium licenses.
- ⇒ Services solely for primary publications are not required to embed these interfaces.
-

R.3-2 The embedding of freely available bibliographical sources supports the upload of secondary publications. ⇒ Suitable data sources are, in particular, arXiv (see <https://arxiv.org>), PubMed (see <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>), PubMedCentral (see <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc>), Crossref (see <https://www.crossref.org>), DataCite (see <https://datacite.org>) and INSPIRE-HEP (see <https://inspirehep.net>).

⇒ A data import (e.g. BibTeX, RIS) is also an option here.

R.3-3 Operators offer contributors the option to include ORCID iDs in metadata.

⇒ The ORCID API's authentication function (freely available through the public API) should be used for this to ensure an author is linked reliably to a publication.

R.3-4 Workflows are offered to assist publishers with extensive publication projects. Information about this should be provided on the service's website.

⇒ This largely involves processes and systems facilitating a peer review for electronic journals or scientific conferences.

R.3-5 Specific information is offered about citation of the offered electronic documents.

⇒ This should communicate that electronic publications should be cited using a persistent identifier system. Recommendations can also be made on how to reference specific sections of a document without any page numbering.

⇒ Example: Doe, John: title, sections 2–4. In: editor: collection title, city, publisher, year.
URL: <https://doi.org/xx.xxxx/abc>.

R.3-6 The operating institution offers information about the Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID iD) and about other author identification standards.

⇒ The information is provided at least via the website and contains a link to the ORCID landing page (<https://orcid.org>).

R.3-7 The available information or parts thereof are also provided in English.

⇒ This is advised especially when addressing authors and/or publishers whose native language is not German.

2.4 Legal Aspects

Operators of an Open Access publication service require certain usage rights from → *rights holders* (typically → *creators*) to offer → *documents* to the public and to facilitate

their long-term archiving. This is formalized in an agreement known as a → *deposit license*.

Legal requirements can differ greatly between primary and secondary publications on repositories.

Other than with → *primary publications*, it must be assumed that with → *secondary publications* the copyright holders (German: *Urheber*innen*) no longer hold all usage rights. Additionally, many secondary publications are added to repositories without prior direct contact to the copyright holder. Generally, the legal basis in such cases is a direct contractual agreement with the publishers or publishing houses as rights holders. Due to the above, the following requirements differentiate in part between primary and secondary publications. Should a service offer only one of the two types of publication, the respective other's requirements do not have to be met. In principle the following applies: For primary publications, the operating institution **must** offer a → *deposit license* or a free license has to be available that grants the necessary rights to the operators. For secondary publications, the provider **can** offer a → *deposit license* or refer to another legal basis (e.g. alliance or national license in Germany, consortium license in Austria, or other free license).

If the basis for the secondary publication is a direct contact with the resp. author(s), the use of a → *deposit license* is advised.

For primary as well as for secondary publications, the operators are free to govern additional aspects in a → *deposit license*. Special importance must be given to free licenses and the use of RightsStatements as standardized vocabulary.

The legal status of the published documents' state of protection must be transparent so users are clear about what needs to be taken into consideration when re-using a published document, and to allow for automatic re-uses of these specifications.

These and other legal aspects to be observed when operating an Open Access publication service are the subjects of this criterion. No statement or remark in this section / criterion is to be understood as legal advice or legally binding information. All service providers are advised to cooperate with their institution's legal department and to seek additional professional advice where legal aspects are concerned.

To ensure compliance with the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), close cooperation with the institution's data security officer is advised.

Minimum Requirements for Primary Publications

M.4-1 The legal relationship between author(s) and publisher(s) (rights holders) and the operating institution is governed in a formal agreement (granting of rights).

⇒ The granting of rights is formalized in a license agreement or a → *deposit license*. The copyright holders grant non-exclusive usage rights to the operators.

⇒ Use of Creative Commons licenses is strongly recommended as they are the current de-facto standard.

⇒ A → *deposit license* is not necessary if the publication is under a free license that grants the necessary rights to the operator. These are mostly Open Definition-compliant licenses such as CC BY (see <https://opendefinition.org/licenses>).

M.4-2 The operators publish the → *deposit license(s)* in the country's official language(s) where the service is based.

⇒ The version(s) in the country's official language is/are legally binding. Other language versions are optional. Legally binding is the version the creator(s) actually agreed to.

By agreeing to the → *deposit license*, the rights holders grant the following usage rights on a document and its metadata (incl. the abstract(s)) to the operators for a primary publication.

M.4-3 The right to store the publication electronically and to make the publication available to the public. Where print-on-demand services are offered, the reproduction and dissemination rights must be granted as well.

M.4-4 The right to notify and transfer the document to third parties, e.g. within the framework of national collection mandates, especially for the purpose of long-term archiving.

⇒ In Germany, law mandates that online publications be supplied to the German National Library (see Law regarding the German National Library (*Gesetz über die Deutsche Nationalbibliothek* – DNBG, see <https://www.dnb.de/pflichtablieferung>) and/or Regional Libraries.

⇒ In Austria, the Austrian National Library may be entitled, but is not legally required, to collect online publications. (Legal provisions on automated collection of online publications in Austria are laid down in Section 43b of the Austrian Media Act (*Mediengesetz* – MedienG, see https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokument.wxe?Abfrage=Erv&Dokumentnummer=ERV_1981_314.)

M.4-5 The right to copy and to convert the document for archiving purposes into additional, different electronic or physical formats while retaining the content's integrity.

⇒ A conversion may, e.g. become necessary should the used data/file formats become obsolete and current presentation/viewing software be unable to present the document correctly.

M.4-6 When submitting a document, the author has the option of selecting a license that defines user rights. A preselection takes standardized license models into account; licenses conforming to the Open Definition are encouraged (see <https://opendefinition.org/licenses>).

⇒ An Open Definition-compliant license is CC BY.

Minimum Requirements for Secondary Publications

M.4-7 The copyright holders express in a documentable and verifiable manner their intention to disseminate an article as a secondary publication using this service. As an alternative, the operators provide documentation confirming that separate permission to secondary publish has been granted.

⇒ The mandate or the agreement to a secondary publication should be in a form that others can comprehend and whose integrity the service provider can verify with reasonable effort (e.g. through a → *deposit license*, authentication in the repository, and agreement to grant rights, documented email exchange).

⇒ Separate permission to secondary publish has been granted if national or alliance licenses, publishing house sublicensing rights, or a free license permit secondary publishing.

⇒ In Germany, Section 38(4) of the German Copyright Act (UrhG) permits secondary publication subject to compliance with legal provisions (since 2014).

⇒ In Austria, Section 37a of the Austrian Copyright Act (UrhG) permits secondary publication subject to compliance with legal provisions (since 2015).

Minimum Requirements for Primary and Secondary Publications

M.4-8 The copyright holders assure the operators that no third-party rights will be violated by publishing the document or parts thereof.

Should third-party rights be asserted following publication, the copyright holders warrant that they will immediately inform the operators thereof.

⇒ Third-party claims may refer to used content (e.g. photographs) or involved persons (e.g. joint copyright holders, co-publishers, publishing houses, funding agencies).

⇒ For primary publications, such terms must be governed in the → *deposit license*.

⇒ For secondary publications, such terms are not required if the operators have reviewed the legal situation or if permission for secondary publication has been granted elsewhere (cf.

M.4-7).

M.4-9 A legal notice is published on the website that meets legal requirements.

⇒ In Germany, such legal requirements are governed in the Telemedia Act (*Telemediengesetz* – TMG) and in state laws.

⇒ In Austria, such legal requirements are laid down in the Media Act (*Mediengesetz* – MedienG).

M.4-10 The operators document the legal attributes of the published documents in their resp. metadata to make them accessible for machine-reading.

⇒ Information on the conditions under which a document may be used by third parties is stored with each published document.

⇒ Machine-readable information is in particular provided via the OAI interface. Additionally, machine-readable information on the rights situation is provided via the web frontend, e.g. as meta-tags in the HTML header or RDFa elements in the HTML body.

⇒ Standardized URLs are used to mark the legal provisions. For documents under a free license, the resp. license's URL is listed in the OAI metadata. For other documents, *RightsStatements* vocabulary URLs are used (see <https://rightsstatements.org>).

⇒ Example 1: CC BY 3.0 DE document; OAI:

<dc:rights><https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/de/></dc:rights>

⇒ Example 2: Copyright protected document (*RightsStatements*); OAI:

<dc:rights><https://rightsstatements.org/page/InC/1.0/></dc:rights>

M.4-11 The legal attributes of the documents are available in machine-readable form on the web frontend to make them accessible for users.

⇒ A description of the conditions under which third parties may use a document is available for every document.

⇒ Should a document be under a free license, a link to the license text is offered.

⇒ For other documents, *RightsStatements* vocabulary URLs are used.

⇒ Example 1: CC BY 4.0 document; Web frontend (one of the following variants or a combination thereof):

(1) [CC-Icon] (Note: The CC icon must not stand alone!)

(2) CC BY 4.0

(3) Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International

⇒ Example 2: Document copyright protected through (*RightsStatements*); Web frontend (one of the following variants or a combination thereof):

(1) [RightsStatements-Icon] (Note: The icon must not stand alone!)

- (2) In Copyright (e.g. link to <https://rightsstatements.org/page/InC/1.0/?language=de>)
(3) Copyright protected

Recommendations for Secondary Publications

R.4-1 The operators document the results of the clarification of copyright issues.

⇒ This refers to, e.g. a publishing house's permission, a clause in the author-publisher contract, or another legal basis which makes it clear that such a secondary publication is allowed (see M.4-7). In case of a conflict, this facilitates verification of the legal validity of the secondary publication.

⇒ This can be noted in the repository metadata, in spreadsheets, a ticketing system (with archiving functionality), on paper or other forms.

⇒ During the certification process, the form of documentation must be made clear to the evaluators.

R.4-2 The copyright holders grant the operators the right to copy and to convert the document for archiving purposes into additional different electronic or physical formats while retaining the content's integrity.

⇒ A conversion may, e.g. become necessary should the used data/file formats become obsolete and current presentation/viewing software be unable to present the document correctly.

Recommendations for Primary and Secondary Publications

R.4-3 If a → *deposit license* is used to grant rights, it should additionally be available online in English.

⇒ Legally binding is the version the creator(s) actually agreed to.

R.4-4 The operators are allowed to transfer rights granted in the → *deposit license*. in full or in part, to third parties and to transfer non-exclusive copyrights to other repositories without the specific consent of the copyright holders.

⇒ This is necessary, e.g. in case the operators cease the provision of (parts of) the service or changes its legal status, while still assuring open public access to the documents through a third party, e.g. an institution specializing in long-term archiving.

R.4-5 The operators license the documents' metadata under CC0 or the Open Data Commons Open Database License (ODbL).

⇒ This free license allows the exchange of metadata between different services and service providers. This is a pre-condition for the development of add-on services that will enhance the attractiveness and visibility of the services.

⇒ For inclusion in the policy, see [Criterion 2, Guidelines \(Policy\)](#), R.2-3.

⇒ For technical integration in the OAI interface, see [Criterion 9 – OAI Interface](#), M.9-6.

2.5 Information Security

To guarantee a reliable service that satisfies the general requirements of scientific publishing, the underlying technical system and the organizational structure must meet basic criteria with regard to information security. These are specified in the *Common Criteria* as published in the international standard ISO/IEC 15408. The main contents are fail safety, operational safety, and trustworthiness of the technical infrastructure, as well as availability, integrity and authenticity of the published documents. The service must be secure against attacks, misuse, operating errors, and technical malfunctions and failures. Organizational and technical measures must be taken to ensure this.

Minimum Requirements

M.5-1 A security concept exists for the technical system that forms the basis for the service.
⇒ This concept identifies and qualifies possible risks and describes technical, organizational and personnel-related provisions to adequately counter these risks. A central hotline and all contacts with their respective responsibilities for the system's security are named.
⇒ The security concept is made available to the evaluators during the certification process.

M.5-2 There is an operations concept in place that includes a technical maintenance plan.
⇒ The operations concept contains descriptions of all tasks, actions and processes necessary to operate the system, as well as the corresponding roles and interfaces.
⇒ The security concept is made available to the evaluators during the certification process.

M.5-3 There is written documentation available on the technical system and all of its components needed for the operation of the system.
⇒ This documentation does not have to be published (at least not in its entirety). Security-relevant elements are for internal use only.
⇒ The documentation is made available to the evaluators during the certification process.

M.5-4 All data and documents are regularly saved in a back-up procedure.
⇒ At what interval back-ups are run depends largely on how often changes are made to the data, i.e. how often new publications are uploaded. It is advised to run a daily and a weekly back-up procedure.

M.5-5 Autonomous software regularly monitors the availability of the servers that are necessary for the service's operation.
⇒ If operation depends on other additional services (e.g. authentication via LDAP), these services should be monitored as well.

M.5-6 Full texts uploaded to the publication service will not be altered.
⇒ Changes to the content of published documents will be considered subsequent versions that do not overwrite or render inaccessible earlier editions.

M.5-7 Every document (and every version) uploaded to and published by the publication service is assigned a Persistent Identifier (PI).

⇒ Available PI systems are, e.g. DOI, URN and Handle.

M.5-8 Persistent identifiers are provided on the service's website and in the exported metadata as primary identifiers, and always in the form of an operable URL.

⇒ This requires a resolving service's URL to be added to the persistent identifier, e.g. <https://doi.org/10.18452/1503> or <https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:kobv:11-100239432>).

As for the metadata export, see also [Criterion 6 – Indexing and Interfaces](#), M.6-6.

⇒ The persistent identifier is made available in human-readable and machine-readable form on the website, and in machine-readable form via OAI (Dublin Core element *identifier*).

M.5-9 Documents are only deleted as an exception and subsequently documented publicly under the persistent URL of the original document.

⇒ This could be the case should the publication constitute a criminal offense.

⇒ In all cases, withdrawal or locking of the document is to be preferred over deletion.

⇒ It is advised not to delete duplicates but to redirect one document's URL to that of the other.

M.5-10 Data exchange between web servers and users during login and the publication process takes place using current TSL technologies, e.g. SSL.

Recommendations

R.5-1 The individual document's integrity is regularly verified through internal processes using a hash value.

R.5-2 Upon publication of a new version of a document, the older version is marked as not current and links to the new version.

⇒ This information is made available in human-readable and machine-readable form on the website, and in machine-readable form via OAI (Dublin Core element *relation*).

2.6 Indexing and Interfaces

To find a document that is published electronically outside the local system, it is crucial for it to be indexed with descriptive metadata which can be automatically processed and have working URLs. At the core of this are referencing and other additional services that third parties provide by using the data and documents provided by the service. Local search services and additional services are also a key aspect of Open Access publication services. This criterion describes the pre-conditions to fulfill these requirements.

Minimum Requirements

M.6-1 There is a written policy containing the indexing regulations for documents that is available online to users (authors, publishers and readers).

- ⇒ It covers, e.g. who does the indexing—library personnel or the authors—or if indexing is performed automatically.
⇒ This policy may vary depending on the publication type.
-

M.6-2 Every document is represented in an indexed form that employs the means and methods of the Dublin Core element set.

- ⇒ It is not mandatory for these metadata to also be stored internally in this format.
-

M.6-3 All documents are classified using the Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC), at least in accordance with the German National Bibliography's subject headings.

- ⇒ See https://www.dnb.de/EN/Professionell/DDC-Deutsch/ddc-deutsch_node.html/ and section 2.10.
-

M.6-4 All documents are assigned document or publication type descriptions following DINI's recommendations in Common Vocabulary for Publication and Document Types (*Gemeinsames Vokabular für Publikations- und Dokumenttypen*).

- ⇒ See <https://doi.org/10.18452/24147> and section 2.10.3.
⇒ The vocabulary from DataCite Schema 4.0 is also recommended for document types.
-

M.6-5 There is a web interface allowing end users to access all published documents and their respective metadata.

- ⇒ This interface allows access to the entire holdings of a service.
-

M.6-6 An OAI interface is integrated that complies with the requirements of OAI-PMH 2.0 and of the DINI OAI Guidelines.

- ⇒ For the DINI OAI Guidelines, see [sections 2.9 OAI Interface](#) and [2.10 OAI-PMH: Additional Requirements](#).
-

M.6-7 A direct export of individual metadata records resp. of search results in at least one suitable data format is available on the website. ⇒ This includes, e.g. the BibTex and EndNote formats as well as the COinS microformat. This function serves the seamless data transfer into reference-management programs such as Citavi or Zotero.

Recommendations

R.6-1 In addition to the German National Bibliography's subject headings, verbal (uncontrolled keywords) or an (interdisciplinary or intradisciplinary) classificatory subject indexing is performed.

- ⇒ Examples are GND, LoC Subject Headings, CCS, MSC and PACS.
⇒ Authors may assign keywords themselves.
-

R.6-2 English keywords are assigned to all metadata sets.

- ⇒ Authors may assign keywords themselves.
-

R.6-3 Short summaries or abstracts in English and German are offered in all metadata sets.
⇒ These may be requested from the authors or extracted from the full texts.

R.6-4 The metadata (e.g. of parts of the holdings) are provided in additional metadata formats and are available via the OAI interface.
⇒ These may be subject or publication-type specific metadata formats for relevant technical or archiving information that facilitate additional services by third parties: One of these is XMetaDissPlus (see https://www.dnb.de/EN/Professionell/Sammeln/Unkoerperliche_Medienwerke/unkoerperliche_medienwerke_node.html) for the delivery of metadata to the German National Library.

R.6-5 Metadata are made publicly available via additional interfaces.
⇒ Examples include SRU/W (see https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Search/Retrieve_via_URL) or specified APIs as well as ResourceSync (see <https://www.openarchives.org/rs/toc>) and signposting (see <https://signposting.org>).

R.6-6 Authors' names are linked to norm data.
⇒ Links are offered to, e.g. the Integrated Authority File (*Gemeinsame Normdatei* – GND, see https://www.dnb.de/EN/Professionell/Standardisierung/GND/gnd_node.html) to facilitate author identification.
⇒ To link to ORCID (see <https://orcid.org>), authentication is used via ORCID's public API and the authenticated ORCID IDs are displayed. Implementation of "authenticate" and "display" are free of charge via the public API.
For the integration of ORCID, see also R.3-3 in [Criterion 3 - Support for authors and publishers](#).

R.6-7 A SWORD API is used for the (semi-)automated import of data into the publication service.
⇒ SWORD (see https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/SWORD_%28protocol%29) is mostly used to transfer publication data from publishers to repositories for secondary publications.

2.7 Open Metrics

Keeping and making metrics open, i.e. public, can be the qualitative, quantitative or technological basis for the evaluation of a service. On the level of individual objects (e.g. articles), information on access, mentions in social media or on the frequency of citations can mirror a document's impact.
If possible, open metrics should be considered for use.

Minimum Requirements

M.7-1 The service keeps a consistent access log as per legal regulations.
This usually involves web-server logs which are anonymized or pseudonymized for long-term archiving, or automatically deleted on a regular basis.
⇒ In Germany, archiving is prescribed by law in Section 15(3) and Section 13(1) of the German Telemedia Act (TMG). In Austria, archiving is required by law as laid down in Section 167(1) of the Austrian Telecommunications Act (TKG).

M.7-2 Automatic access is not logged for usage statistics of individual documents or data.
⇒ This can be done, e.g. by evaluating the web-server log's user agent field, by comparing hits to the robots.txt, by using lists of known robots, or by employing heuristic methods.
⇒ This requirement only applies if statistics are published.

M.7-3 There is publicly available documentation describing the criteria and standard applied to create the statistics.
⇒ COUNTER (see <https://www.projectcounter.org>) is one such current standard. If access figures are published that were not determined by this standard, the documentation must contain a notice stating that these figures are not comparable to those of other services. This is especially the case if access figures are provided for each document.
⇒ This requirement only applies if statistics are published.

Recommendations

R.7-1 Access statistics are listed with every document as dynamic metadata and are publicly available.
⇒ Access figures (e.g. per month) can be linked to from a document's landing page.

R.7-2 "Usage statistics of electronic publications" by the DFG Open Access statistics project and the DINI electronic publishing working group available in German at <https://doi.org/10.18452/1490> are logged in line with the COUNTER standard (see <https://www.projectcounter.org>).

R.7-3 Data transfer to a service provider such as the UsageCounts service from OpenAIRE is supported.
⇒ The respective provider's requirements must be supported (see <https://usagecounts.openaire.eu>).

R.7-4 Alternative metrics on the documents are provided. In most cases, this requires a DOI.
⇒ Crossref offers a free API for this: <https://www.crossref.org/services/event-data>.

R.7-5 Citation figures are displayed for the documents. In most cases, this requires a DOI.
⇒ OpenCitation offers a freely usable corpus as a dump or via an API: <https://opencitations.net>.

2.8 Long-term Archiving

This certificate focuses on Open Access publication services and not on digital long-term archives as dealt with in the DIN 31644 "Information and Documentation Criteria for Trustworthy Digital Long-Term Archives" or ISO 16363 "Trusted Digital Repository". However, certain questions on long-term archiving are also valid for services considered

in this document, especially since the published documents are often transferred to a long-term archiving institution requiring adequate pre-conditions to be met.

Minimum Requirements

M.8-1 A minimum time span of no less than five years is defined in the guidelines (policy) for the availability of documents and their resp. metadata published via the service.

⇒ This definition must form part of the service's policy (see [Criterion 2 – Guidelines \(Policy\)](#), M.2-5).

M.8-2 The guidelines (policy) require(s) original files and possible additional archive copies to be free of any technical protection.

⇒ This includes, above all, mechanisms of a Digital Rights Management (DRM), password protection, or limitations regarding the use of the document (copy and paste, printing). As a result, protective measures are barred as they may interfere with long-term archiving strategies (e.g. migration, emulation).

This definition must form part of the service's policy (see [Criterion 2 – Guidelines \(Policy\)](#), M.2-4).

M.8-3 The guidelines (policy) provide(s) a regulation for the deletion of documents.

⇒ This regulation includes the conditions and the procedures for the deletion of documents, and on the data that may have to be stored beyond a date of deletion. This definition must form part of the service's policy (see [Criterion 2 – Guidelines \(Policy\)](#), M.2-9).

Recommendations

R.8-1 Long-term availability of the documents is ensured.

⇒ To ensure this, the operators cooperate with a DIN 31644-certified or ISO 16363-certified long-term archive or are certified according to this norm. This definition must form part of the service's policy (see [Criterion 2 – Guidelines \(Policy\)](#), Minimum Requirement M.2-6).

R.8-2 The guidelines (policy) stipulate(s) that open file formats facilitating long-term availability are used to store documents.

⇒ This includes PDF/A, ODF, TXT.

This definition must form part of the service's policy (see [Criterion 2 – Guidelines \(Policy\)](#), M.2-4).

2.9 OAI interface

This section contains the requirements for the OAI interface with regard to the DINI Certificate for Open Access publication services. As is the case with the eleven main criteria, the minimum requirements in this section must be met by an Open Access publication service to be certified (see [Criterion 6 – Indexing and Interfaces](#), M.6-6).

Since its publication in 2001, the so-called OAI protocol has become the standard for machine-based and asynchronous exchange of bibliographical metadata between

repositories and with providers of comprehensive services. In this context, the OAI interface is identified as a functional software component that acts as a → *data provider* in the sense of the protocol, i.e. it delivers metadata to → *service providers* when it receives requests in line with the protocol. Such an OAI interface is part of the basic components of many repository software solutions. Examples here include (see <https://duraspace.org/dspace>), ePrints (see <https://www.eprints.org>), MyCoRe (see <https://www.mycore.de>) and OPUS (see <https://www.kobv.de/entwicklung/software/opus-4>), along with a multitude of other systems that manage metadata such as library systems or systems used to publish electronic journals such as Open Journal Systems (OJS, see <https://pkp.sfu.ca>).

With regard to the requirements that have to be met, the OAI protocol offers interoperability at a low level. This has led to widespread dissemination and general acceptance of the protocol in a relatively short time. The downside of this is that it reduces the service providers' options as the protocol specifications say little about the structure and quality of the metadata.

The individual metadata sets must only be made available in the standard format *Dublin Core Simple* whose specification allows that each of the fifteen metadata elements is optional and may be omitted, but may also be used any number of times. Alongside the *Dublin Core Simple* format, we also recommend metadata exports using the *DataCite* schema as this allows more semantic structure to be exported and has already been implemented in numerous publication services when assigning a DOI.

Recommendations are available for the elements' inner structure, such as the formatting of dates or the coding of languages, but they are not binding. And while the OAI protocol includes a mechanism for the logical separation or structuring of a *data provider's* data (the so-called *sets*) that permits the selective *harvesting*, it is up to the *data providers'* operators to define and name these *sets*.

To build a high-quality service based on utilizing data harvested using the OAI protocol (primarily comprehensive referencing services with search and browsing features), additional specifications are called for that will fill the gaps (intentionally) left open by the OAI protocol's specifications. The specifications (see [sections 2.10 OAI-PMH: Additional Requirements](#) and [2.11 Metadata Requirements of the OAI Interface](#)) refer mostly to a definition of the *set* structure and the individual metadata element's content in *Dublin Core* or *DataCite* format. Additionally, some requirements are listed in [section 2.9 OAI Interface](#) that are taken from the protocol's specifications.

Similar to the DINI Certificate's other criteria, the OAI Guidelines list minimum requirements and additional recommendations that the *data provider* of a service is not required to meet to be DINI-certified. However, these recommendations (marked in each section) mirror current best-practice solutions. They are recommended for application in OAI interfaces to optimize the metadata's quality and re-use.

These OAI Guidelines follow and are largely compatible to the guidelines created by the DRIVER EU project (see <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest>) and developed by the Open AIRE EU project (see <https://www.openaire.eu>).

Prerequisite for a functioning data exchange via OAI is a protocol-compliant interface, i.e. compliant with the specifications of the OAI Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) in its current version 2.0 (see <https://www.openarchives.org/OAI/openarchivesprotocol.html>). There are different ways to automatically check existing OAI interfaces' protocol conformity. Primarily the repository

explorer (see <http://oai.clarin-pl.eu>) and the DINI validator (see <https://validator.dini.de> – in German). The latter verifies conformity with the OAI specification and compliance with the OAI policy from the DINI certificate. This verification is done especially if an OAI interface is registered as a data provider with the OAI. The list below emphasizes a few requirements that apply to every OAI interface meeting the protocol specifications. These requirements are given special attention as problems can occur in their implementation.

Minimum Requirements

M.9-1 The OAI interface complies with protocol specification version 2.0.

⇒ All other minimum requirements in this section are derived from this.

M.9-2 The OAI interface is persistently available under the registered base URL and delivers sufficient performance.

⇒ This is a prerequisite for reliable use of the interface by the service providers, and it ensures the minimization of communication problems, specifically aborted harvesting processes.

M.9-3 All replies by the OAI interface are well formed in the XML sense and valid with regard to the XML schema defined in the OAI specification and other XML schemata used for metadata formats.

⇒ This requires a uniform and valid character coding for the entire OAI interface (and all datasets).

⇒ Difficulties arise regularly with error messages in the XML stream sent by databases or applications.

⇒ Even XML-valid error messages can disrupt the incremental harvesting and should be avoided.

M.9-4 The OAI interface supports incremental harvesting correctly.

⇒ Pre-condition for this is that every record contains the time of creation or last update of the metadata in the timestamp element (including the correct time zone) and not, e.g. the date of publication of the described document. Timestamps with fluid time zones (i.e. with no time zone assigned) are to be avoided. The time zone should be added to the date and time in a uniform structure (Berlin normal time should be given as “CET” or “+0100” or “+0100 CET” or “A”), and mixed forms are to be avoided.

⇒ This allows service providers to regularly update their data without having to harvest all metadata records. For this, the data provider must support the parameters *from* and *until* for the OAI requests *ListRecords* and *ListIdentifiers* and deliver the correct subsets of the data accurate to at least the day (YYYY-MM-DD).

M.9-5 The OAI interface uses set information in a consistent form.

⇒ This includes especially that all sets with records assigned to them are delivered with the *ListSets* request, and that all records replying to *ListRecords* and *ListIdentifiers* requests qualified by the set parameter belong to the respective data set according to their header information.

M.9-6 The reply to the *Identify* OAI request offers extensive information on the service.
⇒ This includes especially a service operator's valid email address in the element *adminEmail* and a short description of the service in English in the element *description*.

Recommendations

R.9-1 Operators check the OAI interface at regular intervals with manual tests and validate it with automated tools.

⇒ This ensures early identification of internal problems involving the OAI interface.

R.9-2 When making considerable changes to the OAI interface, information is given to the registries where the OAI interface or the service is registered.

⇒ This allows service providers to react adequately to changes. Relevant alterations in the sense of this recommendation are version changes, a change to the base URL, or software migrations for the service.

⇒ For the relevant registries, see also [Criterion 1 – Visibility of the Service](#).

R.9-3 The element *provenance* is used in the *About* container for the individual metadata records that are delivered with *ListRecords* and *GetRecord* requests.

⇒ Additional information on the metadata's sources can be provided in this container (see <https://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/guidelines-provenance.htm>).

R.9-4 The descriptive information in the OAI responses is in English.

⇒ This includes, e.g. the elements in the response to the *setName* or *ListSets* request.

2.10 OAI-PMH: Additional Requirements

The additional requirements described in this section refer mostly to the set structure that the delivered metadata are placed in (sections 10.1 to 10.4). The structure serves to provide additional standardized information on the documents and to allow selective search queries. This facilitates a better interoperability between services and the providers of comprehensive services that are based on them. Further sections contain recommendations on how to deal with deleted documents and records ([10.5](#)), and on flow control ([10.6](#)).

2.10.1 Open Access Document Set

Services not only publish Open Access documents, but also documents that are only available, e.g. to a user group within an institution, or only contain bibliographical information for referencing. For providers of additional services, it is important to discern and select between Open Access and non-OA documents. To facilitate this, the respective status should be identified in the metadata.

It is also advised to make objects selectively available in a separate set so as to comply with different licenses (in particular CC0-licensed objects), see R.4-5 in [Criterion 4 – Legal Aspects](#)).

Minimum Requirements

M.10-1 A *setSpec* set exists that states “open_access” and contains all metadata records of Open Access documents, i.e. the full text is freely available worldwide via a hyperlink.
 ⇒ Services that offer only Open Access publications must also meet this requirement. In this case the set contains all metadata records.

2.10.2 Sets for disciplinary grouping

To enable a rough disciplinary grouping of metadata sets and the respective documents, in Germany the German National Bibliography’s subject groups as used by the German National Library have become the norm. They are based on the *Dewey Decimal Classification* (DDC) and in principle use its first two items (see https://www.dnb.de/EN/Professionell/DDC-Deutsch/ddc-deutsch_node.html). To allow an external *service provider* using the OAI protocol to perform a pre-selection by subject, the subject groups that the service assigned to the documents must also be assigned to the OAI interface’s set structure.

Minimum Requirements

M.10-2 There is a set structure in accordance with Table 1, and all metadata records—like the documents—are assigned a *setSpec* according to the table used.
 ⇒ It is possible to assign each record to more than one DDC subject group.

Table 1: Name and description of the sets for the subject structure

setSpec	setName	German Description
ddc:000	Generalities, science	Allgemeines, Wissenschaft
ddc:004	Data processing, computer science	Informatik
ddc:010	Bibliography	Bibliografien
ddc:020	Library & information sciences	Bibliotheks- und Informationswissenschaft
ddc:030	General encyclopedic works	Enzyklopädien
ddc:050	General serials & their indexes	Zeitschriften, fortlaufende Sammelwerke
ddc:060	General organization & museology	Organisationen, Museumswissenschaft
ddc:070	News media, journalism, publishing	Nachrichtenmedien, Journalismus, Verlagswesen

ddc:080	General collections	Allgemeine Sammelwerke
ddc:090	Manuscripts & rare books	Handschriften, seltene Bücher
ddc:100	Philosophy	Philosophie
ddc:130	Paranormal phenomena	Parapsychologie, Okkultismus
ddc:150	Psychology	Psychologie
ddc:200	Religion	Religion, Religionsphilosophie
ddc:220	Bible	Bibel
ddc:230	Christian theology	Theologie, Christentum
ddc:290	Other & comparative religions	Andere Religionen
ddc:300	Social sciences	Sozialwissenschaften, Soziologie, Anthropologie
ddc:310	General statistics	Allgemeine Statistiken
ddc:320	Political science	Politik
ddc:330	Economics	Wirtschaft
ddc:333.7	Natural resources, energy and environment	Natürliche Ressourcen, Energie und Umwelt
ddc:340	Law	Recht
ddc:350	Public administration	Öffentliche Verwaltung
ddc:355	Military science	Militär
ddc:360	Social services, association	Soziale Probleme, Sozialdienste, Versicherungen
ddc:370	Education	Erziehung, Schul- und Bildungswesen
ddc:380	Commerce, communications, transport	Handel, Kommunikation, Verkehr
ddc:390	Customs, etiquette, folklore	Bräuche, Etikette, Folklore
ddc:400	Language, linguistics	Sprache, Linguistik
ddc:420	English	Englisch
ddc:430	Germanic	Deutsch
ddc:439	Other Germanic languages	Andere germanische Sprachen

ddc:440	French, Romance languages in general	Französisch, romanische Sprachen allgemein
ddc:450	Italian, Romanian, Rhaeto-Romanic	Italienisch, Rumänisch, Rätoromanisch
ddc:460	Spanish & Portuguese languages	Spanisch, Portugiesisch
ddc:470	Italic Latin	Latein
ddc:480	Hellenic languages Classical Greek	Griechisch
ddc:490	Other languages	Andere Sprachen
ddc:491.8	Slavic languages	Slawische Sprachen
ddc:500	Natural sciences & mathematics	Naturwissenschaften
ddc:510	Mathematics	Mathematik
ddc:520	Astronomy & allied sciences	Astronomie, Kartografie
ddc:530	Physics	Physik
ddc:540	Chemistry & allied sciences	Chemie
ddc:550	Earth sciences	Geowissenschaften
ddc:560	Paleontology, paleozoology	Paläontologie
ddc:570	Life sciences	Biowissenschaften, Biologie
ddc:580	Botanical sciences	Pflanzen (Botanik)
ddc:590	Zoological sciences	Tiere (Zoologie)
ddc:600	Technology (Applied sciences)	Technik
ddc:610	Medical sciences, medicine	Medizin, Gesundheit
ddc:620	Engineering & allied operations	Ingenieurwissenschaften und Maschinenbau
ddc:621.3	Electric engineering	Elektrotechnik, Elektronik
ddc:624	Civil engineering	Ingenieurbau und Umwelttechnik
ddc:630	Agriculture	Landwirtschaft, Veterinärmedizin
ddc:640	Home economics & family living	Hauswirtschaft und Familienleben
ddc:650	Management & auxiliary services	Management

ddc:660	Chemical engineering	Technische Chemie
ddc:670	Manufacturing	Industrielle und handwerkliche Fertigung
ddc:690	Buildings	Hausbau, Bauhandwerk
ddc:700	The arts	Künste, Bildende Kunst allgemein
ddc:710	Civic & landscape art	Landschaftsgestaltung, Raumplanung
ddc:720	Architecture	Architektur
ddc:730	Plastic arts, sculpture	Plastik, Numismatik, Keramik, Metallkunst
ddc:740	Drawing & decorative arts	Grafik, angewandte Kunst
ddc:741.5	Comics, cartoons	Comics, Cartoons, Karikaturen
ddc:750	Painting & paintings	Malerei
ddc:760	Graphic arts, printmaking & prints	Druckgrafik, Drucke
ddc:770	Photography & photographs	Fotografie, Video, Computerkunst
ddc:780	Music	Musik
ddc:790	Recreational & performing arts	Freizeitgestaltung, Darstellende Kunst
ddc:791	Public performances	Öffentliche Darbietungen, Film, Rundfunk
ddc:792	Stage presentations	Theater, Tanz
ddc:793	Indoor games & amusements	Spiel
ddc:796	Athletic & outdoor sports & games	Sport
ddc:800	Literature & rhetoric	Literatur, Rhetorik, Literaturwissenschaft
ddc:810	American literature in English	Englische Literatur Amerikas
ddc:820	English & Old English literatures	Englische Literatur
ddc:830	Literatures of Germanic languages	Deutsche Literatur
ddc:839	Other Germanic literatures	Literatur in anderen germanische Sprachen
ddc:840	Literatures of Romance languages	Französische Literatur

ddc:850	Italian, Romanian, Rhaeto-Romanic literatures	Italienische, rumänische, rätoromanische Literatur
ddc:860	Spanish & Portuguese literatures	Spanische und portugiesische Literatur
ddc:870	Italic literatures Latin	Lateinische Literatur
ddc:880	Hellenic literatures Classical Greek	Griechische Literatur
ddc:890	Literatures of other languages	Literatur in anderen Sprachen
ddc:891.8	Slavic literatures	Slawische Literatur
ddc:900	Geography & history	Geschichte
ddc:910	Geography & travel	Geografie, Reisen
ddc:914.3	Geography & travel Germany	Geografie, Reisen (Deutschland)
ddc:920	Biography, genealogy, insignia	Biografie, Genealogie, Heraldik
ddc:930	History of the ancient world	Alte Geschichte, Archäologie
ddc:940	General history of Europe	Geschichte Europas
ddc:943	General history of Europe Central Europe Germany	Geschichte Deutschlands
ddc:950	General history of Asia Far East	Geschichte Asiens
ddc:960	General history of Africa	Geschichte Afrikas
ddc:970	General history of North America	Geschichte Nordamerikas
ddc:980	General history of South America	Geschichte Südamerikas
ddc:990	General history of other areas	Geschichte der übrigen Welt

2.10.3 Document and Publication Type Set

Document type and publication type are a document's important metadata. For a *service provider* to request certain document types (e.g. dissertations), *data providers* must ensure a corresponding *set* structure. The basis for this *set* structure is the common vocabulary developed for the metadata format XMetaDissPlus and for the DINI Certificate. It is published in the DINI Recommendation *Gemeinsames Vokabular für Publikations- und Dokumenttypen* (see <https://doi.org/10.18452/24147>).

In the present DINI Certificate, the set structure is based on the revised version (2.0) of the *Gemeinsames Vokabular* from March 2022. The main changes from the previous version are:

- a set of new publication and document types;
- capitalization of terms has been standardized and now follows the format GkkkGkk, e.g. “*MovingImage*”;
- The “*review*” type has been renamed “*recension*” to distinguish it from the new “*ReviewArticle*” type.

Minimum Requirements

M.10-3 There is a structure in accordance with Table 2, and all metadata records are assigned a *setSpec* according to the document and publication types.

⇒ As stated in the DINI Recommendation *Gemeinsames Vokabular für Publikations- und Dokumenttypen*, assigning a document to more than one document or publication type is recommended (see example 1 below).

Table 2: Name and description of the sets for the formal structure

setSpec	setName	German Description
doc-type:Preprint	Preprint	Preprint
doc-type:WorkingPaper	WorkingPaper	Arbeitspapier
doc-type:Article	Article	Wissenschaftlicher Artikel
doc-type:ResearchArticle	ResearchArticle	Forschungsartikel
doc-type:ReviewArticle	ReviewArticle	Übersichtsartikel
doc-type:Corrigendum	Corrigendum	Korrigendum
doc-type:DataPaper	DataPaper	Data Paper
doc-type:SoftwarePaper	SoftwarePaper	Softwareartikel
doc-type:Editorial	Editorial	Vorwort
doc-type:LetterToTheEditor	LetterToTheEditor	Letter to the editor
doc-type:ContributionToPeriodical	ContributionToPeriodical	Beitrag zu einem Periodikum
doc-type:PeriodicalPart	PeriodicalPart	Teil eines Periodikums
doc-type:Periodical	Periodical	Periodikum
doc-type:Book	Book	Buch

doc-type:BookPart	BookPart	Teil eines Buches
doc-type:Monograph	Monograph	Monographie
doc-type:EditedCollection	EditedCollection	Sammelband
doc-type:SourceEdition	SourceEdition	Quellenedition
doc-type:Manuscript	Manuscript	Handschrift oder Manuskript
doc-type:StudyThesis	StudyThesis	Studienarbeit
doc-type:BachelorThesis	BachelorThesis	Abschlussarbeit (Bachelor)
doc-type:MasterThesis	MasterThesis	Abschlussarbeit (Master)
doc-type:DoctoralThesis	DoctoralThesis	Dissertation oder Habilitation
doc-type:PhDThesis	PhDThesis	Dissertation
doc-type:Habilitation	Habilitation	Habilitation
doc-type:ConferenceObject	ConferenceObject	Konferenzveröffentlichung
doc-type:ConferenceProceedings	ConferenceProceedings	Conference Proceedings
doc-type:ConferenceSlides	ConferenceSlides	Konferenzfolien
doc-type:ConferencePaper	ConferencePaper	Konferenzpaper
doc-type:ConferencePoster	ConferencePoster	Konferenzposter
doc-type:MeetingAbstract	MeetingAbstract	Meeting Abstract
doc-type:Lecture	Lecture	Vorlesung
doc-type:Recension	Recension	Rezension
doc-type:Annotation	Annotation	Entscheidungs- oder Urteilsanmerkung
doc-type:Patent	Patent	Patent, Norm, Standard
doc-type:Report	Report	Verschiedenartige Texte
doc-type:MusicalNotation	MusicalNotation	Noten (Musik)
doc-type:Sound	Sound	Ton
doc-type:Image	Image	Bild
doc-type:MovingImage	MovingImage	Bewegte Bilder

doc-type:StillImage	StillImage	Einzelbild
doc-type:CourseMaterial	CourseMaterial	Lehrmaterial
doc-type:Website	Website	Website
doc-type:Software	Software	Software
doc-type:CartographicMaterial	CartographicMaterial	Kartographisches Material
doc-type:ResearchData	ResearchData	Forschungsdaten
doc-type:PartOfADynamicWebResource	PartOfADynamicWebResource	Teil einer dynamischen Ressource
doc-type:DynamicWebResource	DynamicWebResource	Dynamische Online-Ressource
doc-type:Other	Other	Verschiedenartige Ressourcen, nicht textgeprägt
doc-type:Text	Text	Text

Example 1: Possible set information in the header as given in response to ListRecords, GetRecords or ListIdentifiers requests.

Example 1 shows a possible header of a record provided via the OAI-PMH that meets the requirements listed above in sections 2.9 to 2.11. The record belonging to this header describes a published Open Access scientific article in mathematics.

```

<identifier>oai:MyRepository.de:423569</identifier>
<timestamp>2013-10-01T12:45:01Z</timestamp>
<setSpec>open_access</setSpec>
<setSpec>doc-type:Article</setSpec>
<setSpec>doc-type:Text</setSpec>
<setSpec>ddc:510</setSpec>
<setSpec>status-type:publishedVersion</setSpec>
  
```

2.10.4 Publication Status Set

Open Access publication services may contain documents at various different stages of a publication process. A correlation may exist between this status and a document's quality. Consequently, a rough identification of a document's status or version is preferable. As in different fields of science, there are different methods of contextual evaluation and quality-assurance processes, meaning that only a very rough structure of an evaluation status is prescribed that includes *peer review* and other reviewing methods such as an *editorial review*. The *set* structure follows the *Version Vocabulary* in the DRIVER Guidelines (see <https://wiki.surfnet.nl/display/DRIVERguidelines/Version+vocabulary>).

Recommendation

R.10-1 There is a set structure in accordance with Table 3, and all metadata records are assigned a *setSpec* according to the documents' status in the publication process.

Table 3: Name and description of the sets for the evaluation status

setSpec	setName	German Description
status-type:draft	draft version	Eine frühere Version, die als in Arbeit befindlich in Umlauf gesetzt wurde.
status-type:submittedVersion	submitted version	Die Version, die bei einer Zeitschrift eingereicht wurde, um durch Fachleute begutachtet zu werden.
status-type:acceptedVersion	accepted version	Die Version, die vom Autor/von der Autorin erstellt wurde, in die die Anmerkungen der Gutachter*innen eingeflossen sind und die zur Veröffentlichung angenommen wurde.
status-type:publishedVersion	published version	Die Version, die veröffentlicht wurde.
status-type:updatedVersion	updated version	Eine Version, die seit der Veröffentlichung aktualisiert wurde.

2.10.5 Deleted Documents

In principle, documents that are published by a service are not to be deleted. However, there may be reasons justifying a document's deletion in certain cases, see also M.2-5 in [Criterion 2 – Guidelines \(Policy\)](#). Incremental *harvesting* by service providers may not reveal information about deleted documents—and deleted metadata records—to OAI-based service providers. The OAI protocol's specifications do not lay down which information a *data provider* has to provide for deleted documents, but offer a number of options that every *data provider* can define as a *deleting strategy* and must transmit with the replies to OAI *Identify* requests.

Minimum Requirements

M.10-4 One of the values "persistent" or "transient" is selected as the deleting strategy for the data provider.

⇒ The OAI-PMH permits the options "no", "persistent" and "transient".

- ⇒ If “no” is selected, no information on deleted documents is transmitted, which can lead to inconsistent data on the service provider’s side.
 - ⇒ If the option “transient” is used for deleted documents, the corresponding metadata records have to be available for at least one month after deletion indicating that the document has been deleted.
 - ⇒ If the option “persistent” is used for deleted documents, the metadata remain unchanged, even if the objects no longer exist.
-

M.10-5 Functionality of the *resumption token* is guaranteed.

- ⇒ As problems with the handling of *resumption tokens* may occur (unanswered or incorrect follow-up requests), functionality should be tested explicitly.
- ⇒ If a data package is delivered incomplete, the *resumption token* usually delivered at the end of a package will be missing. To allow repetition of a data package, it must be possible to use *resumption tokens* repeatedly, leading to the same result.

2.10.6 Data Flow Control

The OAI protocol offers data flow control to avoid having to deliver large amounts of data in response to OAI requests. The data provider can define a *harvest batch size*, i.e. the maximum number of metadata records to be delivered in one batch to *ListRecords* or *ListIdentifiers* requests. If the number of hits is greater than the number defined, a *Resumption Token* is transmitted with the reply, which permits continuation of the delivery. The protocol specifications leave it to the data provider to decide what size of packages to deliver, for how long to continue a delivery, or whether to use this option at all.

Recommendations

R.10-2 The *harvest batch size* (i.e. the maximum number of data sets

in response to a *ListRecords* OAI request) is no less than 100 and no more than 500.

- ⇒ Smaller data packages increase the number of required OAI requests, in turn increasing communication duration and the risk of errors. Larger packages carry the risk of transmission errors.
-

R.10-3 The *resumption token*’s life span is at least 24 hours.

⇒ The attribute *expirationDate* describes the time until which the data provider guarantees the continuation of incomplete replies. If this time span is too short, it can cause the cancellation of the entire harvesting process as it expires before the previous reply has been delivered completely.

- ⇒ The *expirationDate* is to be provided as defined in M.9-4.
-

R.10-4 The attribute *completeListSize* is used.

⇒ This describes the number of datasets in the result list which includes important information for the steering and controlling of the entire harvesting process. According to the OAI protocol, however, this is optional.

2.11 Metadata Requirements of the OAI Interface

The minimum standard in the OAI protocol states that metadata must be in the *Dublin Core Simple* format. However, no specifications are given for the precise usage of the individual elements and their inner structures. The following requirements and recommendations on the use of *Dublin Core* for the OAI interface serve to ensure a minimum of interoperability on a metadata level.

However, everyday practice has shown that this format's advantage of flexibility leads to a certain lack of precision, which may result in a lesser quality of the metadata. The elements' commutativity in OAI, combined with the lack of a specification of an inner structure (which XML would enable, but OAI does not standardize), leads to various implementations outside of the specification. In view of this, some metadata should also be provided in an alternative specification: DataCite.

Minimum Requirements

M.11-1 The Dublin Core formatted metadata sets (oai_dc) contain at least the elements *creator*, *title*, *date*, *type* and *identifier*, including their respective contents.
⇒ The elements are necessary for a minimal description of electronic academic documents.
⇒ This requirement only applies when the elements make sense within the set's context.

M.11-2 In every used DC element, exactly one value is referenced.
⇒ Every DC element can be used multiple times within a metadata set.
⇒ Every author's name should be listed in a single *creator* element, every keyword in one single *subject* element, every URL in a single *identifier* element, etc.
⇒ This allows a clear separation of the individual elements and the correct indexing.

M.11-3 Every record referring to full text contains at least *one identifier* element with an operable URL based on a *persistent identifier*.
⇒ This operable URL may lead to a landing page or directly to the full text.
⇒ To transform a persistent identifier (e.g. URN or DOI) into a working URL, the resolving service's base URL must precede it (see [Criterion 5 – Information Security](#), Minimum Requirements M.5-7 and M.5-8).
⇒ Additional *identifier* elements may contain differing URLs for a document's landing page or for alternative versions (e.g. in a different file format), or they may contain different identifiers (e.g. ISBN, ISSN, INSPIRE ID, arXiv Identifier). Identifiers of alternative versions may be added in the *relation* element.

M.11-4 The *creator* element has the inner structure: last name, first name.
⇒ The same is true for the *contributor* element when it contains a personal or institution's name.

M.11-5 Document or publication types according to the DINI Recommendations Common Vocabulary for Publication and Document Types (*Gemeinsames Vokabular für Publikations- und Dokumenttypen*) are assigned to all documents using the *type* element.

- ⇒ The DINI Recommendation supports the listing of a value from the *Dublin Core Type Vocabulary* in a *type* element of its own.
- ⇒ For vocabulary, see the first column in Table 2, [section 2.10.3](#).
-

- M.11-6** Every record contains at least one DNB subject group in a *subject* element, and the document is listed in that group.
- ⇒ For vocabulary, see the first column in Table 1, [section 2.10.2](#).
-

- M.11-7** The *language* element's content is listed according to ISO 639-3.
- ⇒ For German the code is *ger* (ISO 639-2) or *deu* (ISO 639-3), for English it is *eng* in both cases.
-

- M.11-8** The *date* element's content is listed according to ISO 8601.
- ⇒ The corresponding format is YYYY-MM-DD.
-

- M.11-9** In the case, the described document is also described with DataCite, as a minimum, the properties *identifier*, *creator*, *title*, *publisher*, *PublicationYear* and *ResourceType* are given.
- ⇒ These must be filled identical to the fields in Dublin Core.
- ⇒ According to the DataCite schema, the *identifier* field must contain a valid DOI.
-

Recommendations

- R.11-1** The *identifier* elements' order in a metadata record mirrors their importance. The preferred value is given first.
- ⇒ Many service providers read the position as a marker for the priority given to a URL. From the Open Access publication service operator's perspective, the link to the landing page is usually the preferred one.
- ⇒ Formally, the order of elements is of no importance in Dublin Core, but adhering to the rule above has proven to be practicable to "recommend" the preferred URL to the service provider.
-

- R.11-2** The *contributor* element is used and contains the name of a person or institution that was involved in the creation of the document described.
- ⇒ This may be the referee of a dissertation or the editor of a collection.
-

- R.11-3** The *relation* element is used to name objects that are related to the document described.
- ⇒ Relations may be hierarchical structures (*isPartOf*) or updates (*isVersionOf*).
- ⇒ *Identifiers* for such related objects may also be provided in the *relation* field.
-

- R.11-4** The *subject* element is used for descriptions of a document's content.
- ⇒ In general, the content is described using keywords, or notations from classification schemas.
-

R.11-5 The *date* element is used only once in a metadata record.

⇒ The publication date is to be preferred over other dates (e.g. upload date or date of creation) as it has the greatest priority for end users.

R.11-6 If an aggregating service makes multiple services' metadata available, the aggregating service has to offer the option to harvest each service individually. This can be done by grouping *sets* or separate base URLs.

⇒ The aggregator's interface should allow listing and correlating of the included independent services and their resp. institutions.

⇒ Special emphasis is to be put on the aggregated data's normalization, up-to-dateness and duplicate checks.

R.11-7 A direct link to the full text is supplied in an *identifier* element.

⇒ Use of a persistent identifier (incl. preceding resolver) is to be preferred (see M.11-3).

⇒ Other than a link to the landing page, this additional direct link to the full text allows it to be used for external add-on services (e.g. comprehensive full-text searches, text mining).

R.11-8 In addition to the document or publication type, an appropriate pair of values from the hierarchically structured COAR Resource Type Vocabulary is given in a *type* element.

⇒ The COAR Resource Type Vocabulary facilitates international harmonization of document and publication types.

⇒ The type is defined through referencing of the concept URL and label in accordance with https://vocabularies.coar-repositories.org/documentation/resource_types/

R.11-9 For the *creator* element, author identifiers (e.g. ORCID ID) will be integrated in the following inner structure: *Carberry, Josiah; https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1825-0097; https://myAuthorIdentifier/xyz.*

⇒ This recommendation applies to the *contributor* element as well if a person's name is listed in it and if one or more author identifiers are available.

R.11-10 The *rights* element is used to describe the legal (copyright) situation of an object. This includes the Open Access status as well as the license conditions.

The requirements laid down in [Criterion 4 – Legal Aspects](#), M.4-10 must be followed when it comes to license conditions, i.e. use the license URL as the operable URL.

The Open Access status is to be labelled in line with the COAR Access Rights vocabulary, (see https://vocabularies.coar-repositories.org/access_rights/).

R.11-11 In addition to a description in *Dublin Core simple* formatted metadata sets, the object is described by metadata that adhere to the *DataCite* metadata schema in at least version 4.2 (<https://schema.datacite.org>).

⇒ The data format is usually named *oai_datacite* in OAI.

Code example

DataCite

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<resource xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xmlns=
"http://datacite.org/schema/kernel-4" xsi:schemaLocation="http://datacite.org/schema/kernel-4
http://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.2/metadata.xsd">
```

```

<identifier identifierType="DOI">10.0000/example</identifier>
<creators>
  <creator>
    <creatorName nameType="Personal">Miller, Elizabeth</creatorName>
    <givenName>Elizabeth</givenName>
    <familyName>Miller</familyName>
    <nameIdentifier schemeURI="http://orcid.org/" nameIdentifierScheme="ORCID">0000-0001-5000-0007</nameIdentifier>
    <affiliation>University XY</affiliation>
  </creator>
</creators>
<titles>
  <title xml:lang="en-US">Scientific paper</title>
  <title xml:lang="en-US" titleType="Subtitle">subtitle</title>
</titles>
<publisher xml:lang="en">University XY</publisher>
<publicationYear>2014</publicationYear>
<subjects>
  <subject xml:lang="en-US" schemeURI="http://dewey.info/" subjectScheme="dewey">000 computer science</subject>
</subjects>
<contributors>
  <contributor contributorType="ProjectLeader">
    <contributorName>Carberry, Josiah</contributorName>
    <givenName>Josiah</givenName>
    <familyName>Carberry</familyName>
    <nameIdentifier schemeURI="http://orcid.org/" nameIdentifierScheme="ORCID">0000-0002-1825-0097</nameIdentifier>
    <affiliation>University XY</affiliation>
  </contributor>
</contributors>
<dates>
  <date dateType="Updated" dateInformation="Updated version 2">2019-05-08</date>
</dates>
<language>en-US</language>
<resourceType resourceTypeGeneral="Text">report</resourceType>
<alternateIdentifiers>
  <alternateIdentifier alternateIdentifierType="URL"> https://some-dummy-url.com
</alternateIdentifier>
</alternateIdentifiers>
<relatedIdentifiers>
  <relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="arXiv" relationType="IsReviewedBy" resourceTypeGeneral="Text">arXiv:0706.0001</relatedIdentifier>
</relatedIdentifiers>
<formats>
  <format>application/pdf</format>
</formats>
<version>4.2</version>
<rightsList>
  <rights xml:lang="en-US" rightsURI="https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0">CC BY 4.0</rights>
  <rights xml:lang="en-US" rightsURI="info:eu-repo/semantics/openAccess">Open Access</rights>
</rightsList>
<descriptions>
  <description xml:lang="en-US" descriptionType="Abstract"> Abstract information
</description>
  <description descriptionType="SeriesInformation">Journal of Technology, Vol 6, No 2 (2018)
</description>
</descriptions>
<geoLocations> </geoLocations>
<fundingReferences> </fundingReferences>
</resource>

```

Dublin Core Simple

```

<dc:title>Scientific paper : subtitle</dc:title>
<dc:creator>Miller, Elizabeth; https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5000-0007;
https://myAuthorIdentifier/xyz</dc:creator>
<dc:contributor>Carberry, Josiah; https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1825-0097
</dc:contributor>
<dc:subject>000 computer science</dc:subject>
<dc:subject>ddc:000</dc:subject>

```

```
<dc:description>Abstract information</dc:description>  
<dc:description>Journal of Technology, Vol 6, No 2 (2018)</dc:description>  
<dc:publisher>University XY</dc:publisher>  
<dc:date>2014</dc:date>  
<dc:type>report</dc:type>  
<dc:type>doc-type:report</dc:type>  
<dc:identifier>http://some-dummy-url.com</dc:identifier>  
<dc:identifier>https://dx.doi.org/10.0000/example</dc:identifier>  
<dc:language>eng</dc:language>  
<dc:rights>info:eu-repo/semantics/openAccess</dc:rights>  
<dc:rights>https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0</dc:rights>
```

3 Awarding and Evaluation

The German Initiative for Network Information (DINI) or a working group authorized by DINI is responsible for the awarding of the DINI Certificate for Open Access publication services. The certificate's seal shows the year of its version. The certificate acknowledges that the certificated repository meets the minimum requirements for DINI-certified Open Access publication services.

Application for a DINI certificate is subject to a fee as follows:

1. Not-for-profit organizations
 - a. DINI members: €300.00
 - b. others: €600.00
2. For-profit organizations
 - a. DINI members: €600.00
 - b. others: €1,200.00

The operator/provider of the Open Access publication services applies to DINI for certification by completing an online form on the DINI website. This form has the structure of a checklist and contains the minimum requirements as well as the recommendations laid down in [section 2](#) of this document. The form is available on the DINI website:

<https://dini.de/dienste-projekte/dini-zertifikat/fragebogen>

By completing the form, the providers state that and to what extent the Open Access publication service meets the criteria of the DINI Certificate. Further explanations and clarifications can be added in designated fields in the form, as well as URLs or other options on how or where to receive additional information.

Since the publication of the DINI Certificate 2013, hosting services for Open Access publication services can apply for the acknowledgment that they are [DINI-ready](#), i.e. that all of the services they host meet certain minimum requirements. DINI enters into an agreement with the respective host organizations, which specifies both sides' privileges and obligations. Operators employing a DINI-ready hosting service state this in the application form, and do not have to answer the questions relating to these already met requirements ([see section 1.4 of this document](#)).

After the online form has been completed and submitted, the application and supplied data will be verified; generally, two reviewers will be appointed for this who must be granted access to the services to be certified. The provider must be prepared to answer questions from reviewers. Communication between applicant and reviewer will be deemed confidential unless specified otherwise. On-site visits will only take place in exceptional cases. Any

additional costs incurred during the certification process must be covered by the provider. DINI will inform the provider about possible additional costs beforehand.

Reviewers are typically recruited from previously certified institutions. Newly certified institutions will be requested to name a person as a reviewer. Reviewer teams consist of two people, with one person being from the country of the service under review and at least one person being a DINI member.

The certification process should generally be completed within two months. The duration of the certification process depends in part on how quickly the provider answers any questions the reviewers may have. This process may take longer if any of the criteria are not met.

The DINI Certificate expires upon publication of the third subsequent version of the criteria catalog. Upon publication of the present 2022 version, all of the certificates based on the criteria catalog for 2013 or prior to that will expire.

As the certificate shows the year of the version, it will always be clear which standards applied to an Open Access publication service certification, even if a more recent certificate version exists. DINI is entitled to revoke a certificate if a provider fails to meet minimum requirements after being certified.

Changes to the implementation of a publication service may have an effect in terms of meeting the minimum requirements of the certificate. The operator must inform DINI of any such changes to its publication service. DINI reserves the right to subsequently review the service, to recertify the service, or to revoke certification. This may result in costs to be clarified with the operator in advance.

The provider of the certified service is entitled to call it a “DINI-certified Open Access publication service”, and to display the DINI Certificate’s seal on a web page or in other applicable forms. Any misuse of the seal or certificate will be prosecuted in accordance with applicable laws.

4 Glossary

In this section the most important terms used in this document are named and defined for their use in this document.

Open Access Publication Services / Service / Publication Service

Open Access publication services are the DINI Certificate’s objective. They are comprehensive services for the publication and online provision of scientific and scholarly publications. The service or publication service caters to producers (authors) as well as to recipients (readers) and contains both the technical infrastructure (i.e. hardware and software with certain specificities) and the organizational and legal frame.

In the present document, Open Access repositories and publication services are usually termed “service”.

Certification focuses on the following services:

- Institutional Open Access repositories
- Cross-institutional repositories
- Disciplinary Open Access repositories
- Open Access journals

The following services are not the primary objectives of the certification based on the current version of the DINI Certificate:

- Digital Collections
- Research-Data Repositories
- Research Information Systems (CRIS)
- University Bibliographies

So-called → *Hosting Services* play a special role.

Institutional Open Access Repository

An institutional repository largely holds Open Access full texts of an institution. This includes every kind of scientific/scholarly publication by members of this institution (in particular habilitations, dissertations, Bachelor's and Master's theses) as well as other results (reports, secondary publications, etc.) and materials.

Cross-institutional Repository

A cross-institutional repository collects data from various different institutions or faculties. It can hold every kind of scientific publication or qualification thesis.

Disciplinary Open Access Repository

A disciplinary Open Access repository largely contains Open Access documents of a certain scientific/scholarly discipline. This includes every kind of scientific publication (qualification theses, reports, secondary publications, etc.) and other materials. Disciplinary Open Access repositories offer publications by authors from various different institutions.

Open Access Journal

An Open Access journal is a scientific journal largely containing Open Access articles that fit the journal's profile. At least the majority of articles has undergone a peer-review process. The journal may also contain supportive materials and/or research data. The journal is published by at least one scientist/scholar or a scientific/scholarly institution, or one closely attached to science.

Digital Collection

The term *digital collection* often describes repository systems that present collections of digital objects in a higher education and academic environment. This comprises especially materials such as digitized books and journals, maps, photographs, paintings, music, autographs (manuscripts, letters, postcards), i.e. materials that are often objects of cultural heritage, and historic sources. Accordingly, these services are especially provided in the humanities and by scientific libraries, museums and archives; they complement publication repositories.

Research-data Repository

A research-data repository allows scientists to archive and present their research data in digital form. These data can have different formats (depending on discipline) and can be either the basis for or the result of a research process.

Current Research Information System (CRIS)

A current research information system comprises integrated documentation and reporting systems that represent a research institution's infrastructure and accomplishments. These systems aid in creating reports for and in the steering of research institutions. They also serve to foster transparency of the research system and communication between researchers and the public (see <https://www.dini.de/fis>).

University Bibliography

A university bibliography serves to display an institution's entire publication output (Open Access full texts as well as metadata only). Occasionally, institutional repositories are used for this purpose, but to date the amount of available full texts is small.

Hosting Service

A hosting service is a service for the sciences. *Hosting*—in the sense of the DINI Certificate—is carried out by → *technical operators* of → *Open Access publication services* and includes, at the least, the technical provision, administration and maintenance of the → *service* that is hosted. Additionally, *hosting* may include further support, creating visibility, and consulting/support services. The character of and responsibility for a → *service* is defined by the → *operator* that hires the hosting service.

→ *Hosting Services*—assuming the role of → *technical operators* of services—cannot be directly certified. However, it can be acknowledged beforehand that certain minimum criteria of the DINI Certificate are fulfilled for all of the → *services* that they host. These criteria are marked as *DINI-ready* for all of the services operated by the hosting provider. This makes certification much easier for the → *operators*.

Aggregator

An aggregator is a service that collects (harvests) data from independent → *data providers* (typically via OAI-PMH) before enhancing and basing comprehensive services on them. Data can be regrouped according to regional, disciplinary or any other aspect (e.g. type of publication).

Popular services are the retrieval but also the OAI-PMH-based forwarding of aggregated data. Here, branding of the originating repository, normalization effects, updating, and control of doubles are crucial to the quality of the service.

A known aggregator in Germany is the Bielefeld Academic Search Engine (BASE: <https://www.base-search.net>). National aggregators are also present in Sweden (SWEPUB: <https://swepub.kb.se>), Norway (NORA: <https://www.ub.uio.no/nora/search.html>), the Netherlands (NARCIS: <https://www.narcis.nl>), and in other European countries.

Author/Publisher

In most cases these are the creators and copyright holders of the content offered by a → *service*. For publications with more than one creator where the usage rights have been transferred to only one, this one person holds the right to publish the content. In addition, a publisher is the entity which publishes a journal, i.e. its → *operator*.

Operator, Technical Operator

Institution that is responsible for the provision of → *Open Access publication services*. An operator offers the service to various user groups and answers to the users, even if responsibilities are divided internally or even outsourced. Used synonyms in this document are *provider* and *service provider*. An operator may also be used to refer to the publisher of an → *Open Access journal*. This is not the case with a technical operator, which is only responsible for providing hardware and software. In many instances, these are → *hosting services*. Technical operators and operators can be identical or under the responsibility of the same legal body.

Data Provider

Data providers, in the OAI-PMH's understanding, deliver data, i.e. offer → *documents'* → *metadata* via the OAI interface.

Deposit License

Formal agreement in which the → rights holder (i.e. the author or the publisher) grants certain → *usage rights* to the → *operator* of an → *Open Access publication service* in order to allow the operator to make the respective → *documents* publicly available and to archive them. Moreover, in this agreement the rights holder excludes any infringement of third-party rights. Synonyms used here are *license agreement*, *granting of rights*, *declaration of consent*.

Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC)

DDC is a globally used universal classification system to index content. The → *German National Bibliography's subject headings* are based on the DDC.

Document

Smallest logical entity that is published by → *Open Access publication services*, usually a text-based scientific or scholarly work with clearly named creators. Synonyms used in this text are *electronic document*, *publication*, *work*. The term is to be used comprehensively, and can be replaced by the term *object*, especially in services that focus on data, images, and other digital artefacts.

Document Server

Technical infrastructure of an → *Open Access publication service*, characterized by basic infrastructure components (e.g. network, server, operating system, file system, database, communication system) and the document server software (e.g. DSpace, ePrints, LibreCat, MyCoRe, OJS, OPUS). Synonyms used in this text: *publication server, repository*.

Primary Publication

This is the (chronologically) first publication of a → *document*. A primary publication can, e.g. be a dissertation that is published on a repository, or a scientific article that is published in an Open Access journal. See also: → *Secondary Publication*.

Landing Page

Web page containing metadata of and links to a → *document's* full-text files plus additional functions and information (e.g. social network links, export of bibliographical data in machine-readable formats, print-on-demand services, document-related metrics). Usually the landing page is generated dynamically, its content coming from a database. Synonyms used here are *jump-off page, splash page, front page, front door*.

Metadata

Data for the characterization of an object (in this text mostly → *documents*). Typically, these are divided into descriptive, technical and administrative metadata. Descriptive metadata contain information for formal and subject classification. Metadata can be coded in different formats and are interchangeable. Internally stored metadata do not have to be made available to the public in full (e.g. administrative metadata). Relevant standards for electronic publications are *Dublin Core* (<https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dces>), MARC (<https://www.loc.gov/marc>), MODS (<http://www.loc.gov/standards/mods>) and, especially for data exchange with the German National Library, XMetaDissPlus (<https://www.dnb.de/xmetadissplusnp>).

User

In the DINI Certificate's context a natural person who uses services offered by an → *Open Access publication service*. Users can be split into three groups: Publishers, direct recipients and indirect recipients (readers, researchers). Publishers are document authors and editors. [Criterion 3 – Support of Authors and Publishers](#) provides minimum requirements and recommendations as a guide for publishers. Direct recipients can access the Open Access publication service directly to obtain documents or for research purposes. Indirect recipients can access documents provided by the publication service by way of → *aggregators* and other services. All three user groups should be kept in mind when designing and setting up Open Access publication services.

Usage Rights / Copyright

In the DINI Certificate's context, these are rights that are granted to end users of → *documents* or their → *metadata* that are published by → *Open Access publication services*. Based on German copyright law, usage rights are originally held by the creators, i.e. the authors, and therefore must be transferred with appropriate processes.

Open Access

Worldwide free access to scientific information, especially to scientific and scholarly publications in electronic form and online, as defined, e.g. in the 2003 Berlin Declaration (<https://openaccess.mpg.de/Berlin-Declaration>). A worldwide movement with numerous national and international initiatives is dedicated to the dissemination and to the achievement of the goals of the Berlin Declaration. Typically, two forms of Open Access are differentiated: The green and the golden roads.

The first describes the additional publication of documents already published elsewhere (usually by a publishing house) or slotted for publication as a parallel, → *secondary publication* in a freely available version – usually in a repository.

The golden way is the → *primary publication* with Open Access, e.g. in an Open Access journal. Main examples here include → *Open-Access journals* and German-language university press.

Open Access Policy

Scientific/scholarly institutions' guidelines on how to deal with → *Open Access*. They state, e.g. that Open Access is a desirable publication paradigm for the respective institution, and they encourage authors to publish their documents Open Access.

Persistent Identifier (PI)

Worldwide unambiguous and unchangeable (persistent) name of a digital information object, (for this text) usually an electronic → *document*. Persistent identifiers are especially useful for the citation of electronic publications, as they are permanent (unlike a URL). There are different PI systems available, e.g. URN, DOI and Handle. A PI's syntactical structure is defined in a formal description of the structure. PIs and related URLs must be registered (typically centrally) to facilitate the resolving service that reroutes requests for a URN to the actual physical addresses. PIs can also be natural persons (ORCID: <https://orcid.org>) and institutions (ROR: <https://ror.org>).

Rights Holder

Rights holder is the owner of → *usage rights / copyrights* of a work. Rights holders can be natural persons (usually the → *creator*) or a legal person (e.g. a publishing house). A → *document* may only be published on a publication service with the consent of the rights holder.

Subject Headings of the German National Bibliography

Rough classification of documents into approx. 100 different classes. They are based on the → Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC) and represent a simplified use of this comprehensive system https://www.dnb.de/EN/Professionell/DDC-Deutsch/ddc-deutsch_node.html.

Service Provider

A service provider in the DINI Certificate's context offers comprehensive → services using distributed data that are aggregated via the OAI protocol (e.g. harvester).

Creator

A creator is the person who created a work. In the understanding of this Certificate, these are the → authors who created a → document. The creator is the → rights holder of a → primary publication.

If a work is published by a publishing house, the creator transfers all → usage rights to the publishing house that is then the sole → rights holder. Under certain circumstances, e.g. by granting non-exclusive copyrights or pursuant to Section 38 of the German Copyright Act (UrhG), creators retain the → secondary publication right for the → document.

Other legal bases for secondary publication include, in particular, the reversion of non-exclusive rights to the author after an agreed period (agreement), Open Access rights from formal agreements (in particular alliance or national licenses), a general Open Access-friendly publishing policy, permission granted by a publishing house, and the presence of a Creative Commons license.

Secondary Publication

Parallel or subsequent publication of an already published → document on a repository. These are often articles already published in journals or collections, which—depending on the publishing contract—can be made publicly available on repositories as → Open Access secondary publications. (Pre-prints are a special case as they make content available on repositories before they are published.) See also: → Primary Publication.

Authors

This document is published under the Creative Commons license CC BY 4.0.

See <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/deed.en>

- Daniel Beucke (Chair of DINI Working Group “Electronic Publishing”)
Göttingen State and University Library
beucke@sub.uni-goettingen.de
orcid.org/0000-0003-4905-1936
ror.org/01y9bpm73
- Isabella Meinecke (Chair of DINI Working Group “Electronic Publishing”)
Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Hamburg Carl von Ossietzky
isabella.meinecke@sub.uni-hamburg.de

orcid.org/0000-0001-8337-3619

ror.org/00pwcvj19

- Thomas Severiens (Chair of DINI Working Group “Electronic Publishing”)
Institute of Scientific Information, University of Osnabrück
thomas.severiens@jade-hs.de
orcid.org/0000-0001-6303-5073
- Pascal Becker
The Library Code GmbH
pascal@the-library-code.de
orcid.org/0000-0003-2169-1261
- Ute Blumtritt
TU Chemnitz, University Library
Ute.Blumtritt@Bibliothek.TU-Chemnitz.de
orcid.org/0000-0003-4209-3893
ror.org/00a208s56
- Arvid Deppe
Kassel University Library
deppe@bibliothek.uni-kassel.de
orcid.org/0000-0001-7190-9535
ror.org/04zc7p361
- Gernot Deinzer
University Library of Regensburg
gernot.deinzer@ur.de
orcid.org/0000-0002-7462-3847
ror.org/01eezs655
- Stefan Drößler
Stuttgart University Library
stefan.droessler@ub.uni-stuttgart.de
orcid.org/0000-0001-8071-5070
ror.org/01k97gp34
- Doris Ernst
Institute of Science and Technology Austria
doris.ernst@ist.ac.at
orcid.org/0000-0002-2354-0195
ror.org/03gnh5541
- Daniel Formanek
Medical University of Vienna, University Library
daniel.formanek@meduniwien.ac.at
orcid.org/0000-0002-0269-8022
ror.org/05n3x4p02
- Kathrin Höhner
TU Dortmund University
kathrin.hoehner@tu-dortmund.de
orcid.org/0000-0002-3988-7839
ror.org/01k97gp34

- Marian Miehl
Medical University of Vienna, University Library
marian.miehl@meduniwien.ac.at
- Jochen Schirrwagen
Bielefeld University Library
jochen.schirrwagen@uni-bielefeld.de
orcid.org/0000-0002-0458-1004
ror.org/02hpadn98
- Antonia Schrader
Helmholtz Association, Helmholtz Open Science Office
antonia.schrader@os.helmholtz.de
orcid.org/0000-0001-7080-634X
ror.org/0281dp749
- Tobias Steinke
German National Library
t.steinke@dnb.de
orcid.org/0000-0002-3999-1687
ror.org/01n7gem85
- Friedrich Summann
Bielefeld University Library
friedrich.summann@uni-bielefeld.de
orcid.org/0000-0002-6297-3348
ror.org/02hpadn98
- Marco Tullney
Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology University Library
(TIB)
marco.tullney@tib.eu
orcid.org/0000-0002-5111-2788
ror.org/04aj4c181
- Paul Vierkant
DataCite - International Data Citation Initiative e.V.
paul.vierkant@datacite.org
orcid.org/0000-0003-4448-3844
ror.org/04wxnsj81
- Michaela Voigt
Technische Universität Berlin, University Library
michaela.voigt@tu-berlin.de
orcid.org/0000-0001-9486-3189
ror.org/03v4gjf40
- Jan Weiland
ZBW – Leibniz Information Centre for Economics
j.weiland@zbw.eu
orcid.org/0000-0002-3167-0870
ror.org/03a96gc12

- Alexander Weimar
Library Service Centre Baden-Wuerttemberg (BSZ)
alexander.weimar@bsz-bw.de
orcid.org/0000-0003-0741-1665

Additional authors of earlier versions:

- Ursula Arning
- Dörte Bange
- Margo Bargheer
- Karolin Bove
- Kim Braun
- Stefan Buddenbohm
- Sammy David
- Susanne Dobratz
- Martin Fenner
- Stefan Gradmann
- Thomas Hartmann
- Ulrich Herb
- Eberhard Hilf
- Wolfram Horstmann
- Bruno Klotz-Berendes
- Nikola Korb
- Elmar Mittler
- Marianna Mühlhölzer
- Uwe Müller
- Katja Mruck
- Heinz Pampel
- Peter Schirnbacher
- Birgit Schmidt
- Frank Scholze
- Silke Schomburg
- Matthias Schulze
- Heinrich Stamerjohanns
- Nadine Walger
- Bert Wendland
- Stefan Wolf
- Christoph Ziegler
- Dennis Zielke

Membership application form for DINI e. V.

<https://dini.de/dini/mitglieder/mitgliedsantrag>

Legal notice

The online version of this publication is available at

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8324738>

Publisher: Deutsche Initiative für Netzwerkinformation e. V.

Contact details:

DINI – Deutsche Initiative für Netzwerkinformation e. V.

Geschäftsstelle

c/o Niedersächsische Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Göttingen

37070 Göttingen

Tel.: +49 (0)551 39 33857

Email: gs@dini.de

www.dini.de

Translation from German: Andrew Rennison

Last updated: September 2022